

Ion association of α -alanine bis-biguanidocobalt(III) iodide in methanol + water mixtures at different temperatures

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Conductivity measurements of α -alanine bis-biguanidocobalt(III) iodide have been made in water and varying water + methanol mixtures at 5–40°. The limiting equivalent conductance (Λ_0) and the ion association constant (K_A) for the complex salt in these mixtures have been evaluated using Shedlovsky equation. The K_A s obtained have minimum values at temperature t_{\min} . The results have been discussed in terms of ion-ion, ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions. Thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated to understand the change of the association constants with solvent composition.

The influence of dielectric constant on the ion-pairing process of an electrolyte has been revealed by many workers¹. The observed association constant values are known to be a composite quantity depending on specific and non-specific solute-solvent interactions². Wide temperature range (0–50°) conductivity measurements for electrolyte solutions can give detailed information on ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions³. From conductivity measurements at 5–40° in water and water + methanol (W-M) mixtures we found that weak ion-ion interactions are present and that the K_A s are minimized at characteristic temperature. The present work aims at determining the conductance values of the solutions of the title electrolyte in W-M mixtures at 5–40° to examine the validity of Shedlovsky equation. The K_A and Walden products for the Co^{III} complex have been evaluated in these solvents at the experimented temperatures. These computed values have been used to discuss qualitatively the nature of the ion-ion, ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions of the octahedral Co^{III} complex in W-M mixtures. Temperature variation of the K_A has also been studied to get the thermodynamic parameters, viz. ΔS° , ΔH° and ΔG° as a function of the solvent composition.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data of conductance measurements of 2 : 1 Co^{III} complex in W-M mixtures after solvent correction were analyzed using Shedlovsky extrapolation technique⁴. Shedlovsky method involves the linear extrapolation using eq. (1),

$$\frac{1}{\Lambda S(z)} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_0} + \left(\frac{K_A}{\Lambda_0^2} \right) (C \Lambda f_{\pm}^2 S(z)) \quad (1)$$

where Λ is the equivalent conductance at a concentration c

(g equiv dm⁻³), Λ_0 the limiting equivalent conductance and K_A the observed association constant. The other symbols are given by

$$S(z) = \left(\frac{Z}{2} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{Z}{2} \right)^2} \right)^2, \quad Z = \left[\frac{(\alpha \Lambda_0 + \beta)}{\Lambda_0^{3/2}} \right] (C \Lambda)^{1/2},$$

$$\alpha = \frac{17.147 \times 10^5 w}{(DT)^{3/2}}$$

$$w = z_+ z_- \frac{2q}{1+q^{1/2}}, \quad q = \frac{z_+ z_-}{z_+ + z_-} \frac{\lambda_+ + \lambda_-}{z_+ \lambda_- + z_- \lambda_+},$$

$$\beta = \frac{151.47}{\eta(DT)^{1/2}}$$

z and λ are the valence and conductance of the ions respectively, excluding their sign, D is the dielectric constant of the medium, η the viscosity (c.p.). The degree of dissociation (τ) is related to $S(Z)$ by the equation,

$$\tau = \Lambda S(Z) / \Lambda_0$$

f_{\pm} is the mean activity coefficient of the free ions and was calculated using eq. (2),

$$-\log f_{\pm} = \frac{A z_+ z_- \mu^{1/2}}{1 + B R \mu^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } A = \frac{1.8247 \times 10^6}{(DT)^{3/2}}$$

$$B = \frac{0.5029 \times 10^{10}}{(DT)^{1/2}}$$

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2} \sum_1 (C_1 \tau_1) Z_1^2$$

R is the maximum centre-to-centre distance between the ions in the ion-pair. There exists at present no method of determining the value of R precisely⁵. In order to treat the data in our system the R value is assumed to be $R = a + d$, where a , the sum of crystallographic radii of the ions, is approximately equal to 5 Å and d (Å) is given by⁶

$$d = 1.183 (M/\rho)^{1/3}$$

where M is the molecular weight of the solvent and ρ the density of the solution. For mixed solvents M is replaced by the mole fraction average molecular weight,

$$M_{\text{avg}} = \frac{M_1 M_2}{X_1 M_2 + X_2 M_1}$$

X_1 is the mole fraction of methanol of molecular weight M_1 and X_2 that of water of molecular weight M_2 .

As per Shedlovsky method, an initial value of Λ_0 was obtained from the intercept of the linear Onsager plot of Λ versus $c^{1/2}$. λ_-^0 is obtained from the literature at 25° and at other temperatures it was obtained by using the equation⁷,

$$\lambda_i^0 = \lambda_{25}^0 [1 + \alpha(t - 25)] \quad (3)$$

where α is constant. Using these values of Λ_0 , λ_-^0 , λ_+^0 ; Z , $S(Z)$ and τ values were calculated. The mean activity coefficient f_{\pm} was determined by eq. (2). From the linear plot of $1/\Delta S(Z)$ versus $c\lambda_{\pm}^2 S(Z)$, Λ_0 and K_A were evaluated from the intercept ($1/\Lambda_0$) and the slope (K_A/Λ_0^2), respectively. The procedure was repeated using these new values of Λ_0 and K_A . All calculations were carried out on IBM PC-AT/386. The results of Λ_0 , K_A and $\Lambda_0 \eta_0$ at different temperatures are summarized in Table 1.

The plots of $\log K_A$ vs temperature (t) (Fig. 1) give smooth curves with a minima t_{min} generally at 25°. The relative order of magnitude of $\log K_A$ for the complex salt depends on the temperature which can be reproduced by a quadratic equation⁸ in t ,

$$\log K_A = p(t - t_{\text{min}})^2 + \log K_{A(\text{min})} \quad (4)$$

where t_{min} , $\log K_{A(\text{min})}$ are constants and p corresponds to the curvature of the parabola. The following expressions for the standard entropies and enthalpies of ion association in salt solutions ΔS_{as}^0 and ΔH_{as}^0 can be derived from eq. (4),

$$\Delta S_{\text{as}}^0 = 2.303 R \{ \log K_{A(\text{min})} + p(3t - t_{\text{min}} + 546.3) (t - t_{\text{min}}) \}$$

$$\Delta H_{\text{as}}^0 = 4.605 pR (t + 273.15)^2 (t - t_{\text{min}})$$

$$\Delta G_{\text{as}}^0 = \Delta H_{\text{as}}^0 - T\Delta S_{\text{as}}^0$$

As expected, the values of Λ_0 increase invariably with increase in temperature (Fig. 2) in all solvents irrespective of X_{MeOH} , indicating less solvation or higher mobility of ions. This is attributed to the fact that increased thermal energy

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of the ion-association constants between $[\text{Co}(\alpha\text{-ala})(\text{BigH}_2)_2]^{2+}$ and I^- in different mixed solvents of methanol + water (\blacktriangle) $X_{0.000}$, (\triangle) $X_{0.058}$, (\blacksquare) $X_{0.128}$, (\square) $X_{0.194}$, (\bullet) $X_{0.273}$ and (\circ) $X_{0.360}$ in methanol

results in greater bond-breaking, and variation in vibrational, rotational and translational energy of the molecules that leads to higher frequency and hence higher mobility of ions.

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of molar conductance at infinite dilution in different mixed solvents of methanol + water (\circ) $X_{0.0}$, (\bullet) $X_{0.1}$ and (\blacktriangle) $X_{0.36}$

The variation of $\Lambda_0 \eta_0$ and η with the mole fraction of methanol is shown in Fig. 3. The viscosity of W-M mixtures increases upto $X_{\text{MeOH}} = 0.36$ and thereafter it decreases. Values of Λ_0 of the salt decrease upto this mole fraction and

Table 1. Values of limiting equivalent conductances Λ_0 (S cm²), association constant K_A (dm³ mol⁻¹), Walden product $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ and effective radius r (Å) obtained by Shedlovsky technique for octahedral Cd^{II} complex α -alanine bis-biguanide-Co^{II} iodide in water + methanol mixtures at different temperatures

X_{methanol}	Λ_0	$(T = 278.15 \text{ K})$			Λ_0	$(T = 283.15 \text{ K})$			
		K_A	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$	r		K_A	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$	r	
0.0000	390.26	212.36	593.26	3.21	427.17	185.40	556.60	3.37	
0.0588	348.27	233.17	622.70	3.06	360.40	204.16	582.77	3.22	
0.1233	291.08	255.03	629.90	3.03	301.89	220.25	592.61	3.16	
0.1942	264.04	280.75	633.95	3.01	274.91	255.38	599.30	3.13	
0.2727	245.90	331.39	644.75	2.96	258.20	280.22	604.19	3.10	
0.3600	225.33	340.15	655.48	2.91	248.99	312.58	620.24	3.02	
0.4576	254.47	380.26	593.17	3.22	268.69	352.63	575.63	3.26	
0.5676	255.09	420.15	579.31	3.29	270.20	390.07	535.00	3.50	
0.6923	289.51	467.71	476.25	4.01	306.57	426.85	452.50	4.14	
0.8351	313.51	512.44	362.73	5.26	339.70	475.28	360.42	5.20	
1.0000	342.50	563.17	251.40	7.59	375.35	528.34	257.33	7.28	
		$(T = 288.15 \text{ K})$				$(T = 293.15 \text{ K})$			
0.0000	458.62	140.31	520.08	3.54	484.43	125.52	484.97	3.73	
0.0588	375.40	165.96	542.84	3.39	401.36	143.34	502.90	3.60	
0.1233	315.16	185.44	555.32	3.32	341.70	170.20	518.02	3.49	
0.1942	288.23	215.32	564.65	3.26	315.48	187.24	530.01	3.41	
0.2727	280.99	240.21	578.27	3.18	312.06	210.53	552.35	3.28	
0.3600	282.26	272.27	585.12	3.15	311.45	240.35	559.99	3.23	
0.4576	285.70	305.30	556.83	3.31	313.00	275.20	526.15	3.44	
0.5676	290.52	350.52	490.69	3.75	314.86	315.10	476.38	3.80	
0.6923	328.04	385.51	428.75	4.29	339.76	355.35	405.00	4.47	
0.8351	371.01	430.64	358.02	5.14	406.90	395.40	355.63	5.09	
1.0000	420.67	481.07	268.10	6.87	476.31	441.50	281.50	6.43	
		$(T = 298.15 \text{ K})$				$(T = 303.15 \text{ K})$			
0.0000	539.28	110.22	480.50	3.70	596.48	126.15	475.99	3.68	
0.0588	449.86	125.20	493.95	3.60	493.89	142.54	485.00	3.61	
0.1233	386.38	140.17	508.48	3.50	435.75	156.84	498.93	3.51	
0.1942	360.98	164.38	521.25	3.41	407.72	185.41	512.50	3.42	
0.2727	356.97	187.18	536.18	3.32	391.27	215.21	520.45	3.37	
0.3600	345.22	215.34	542.70	3.28	385.47	245.37	525.40	3.33	
0.4576	348.57	240.45	509.26	3.49	388.00	270.18	492.37	3.55	
0.5676	350.31	274.64	469.07	3.79	390.00	310.72	461.76	3.79	
0.6923	372.34	310.53	402.50	4.42	415.00	350.14	400.06	4.37	
0.8351	438.28	356.49	352.82	5.04	482.09	391.66	350.00	5.00	
1.0000	505.45	407.55	279.51	6.37	552.00	437.08	284.28	6.16	
		$(T = 308.15 \text{ K})$				$(T = 313.15 \text{ K})$			
0.0000	656.11	152.68	472.40	3.64	716.88	170.11	468.84	3.61	
0.0588	544.57	167.07	476.50	3.61	595.61	190.08	472.32	3.59	
0.1233	485.93	186.20	490.30	3.51	534.00	214.37	481.67	3.52	
0.1942	452.52	229.33	502.75	3.42	498.48	245.07	493.00	3.44	
0.2727	436.13	243.08	504.60	3.41	495.51	270.18	497.03	3.41	
0.3600	424.21	277.37	508.21	3.39	480.38	312.42	502.00	3.38	
0.4576	425.30	310.05	490.80	3.51	489.70	347.27	488.23	3.47	
0.5676	429.60	348.40	454.52	3.79	472.77	385.33	447.24	3.79	
0.6923	455.85	375.22	397.50	4.33	503.58	430.40	394.81	4.29	
0.8351	515.90	427.30	347.20	4.96	554.90	485.08	344.04	4.92	
1.0000	580.40	485.03	280.33	6.14	620.42	543.17	279.81	6.05	

then increase in methanol-rich region at all the temperatures from 5 to 40° as expected from Walden rule. The maximum in η vs mole fraction indicates maximum interaction between water and methanol in such solvent mixtures.

Fig. 3 The Walden product ($\Lambda_0\eta_0$) and viscosity (η) as a function of $X_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}}$ the mole-fraction of methanol in methanol + water (O) 15°, (\blacktriangle) 25° and (\square) 40°, η at (\bullet) 25°

The Walden product ($\Lambda_0\eta_0$) increases upto a mole fraction of 0.36 in methanol and then decreases. If change in solvation is reflected by the variation in $\Lambda_0\eta_0$, the increase of the product indicates the weak solvation of the ions. The decrease of the product indicates an increase of the hydrophobic solvation with increasing concentration of methanol. As the methanol content increases, progressive disruption of water structure occurs and the ions become solvated with the other component of the solvent mixture (viz. methanol). Further, the effect would be more in case of a solution at a higher temperature. This trend is observed in our experiment (Fig. 3). The experimentally determined K_A s are found to increase with increase in X_{MeOH} (linear plots) which indicates an increased association as methanol is added to water.

Walden product of an ion or a solute is inversely proportional to the effective radius of ion or solute in a given solvent or solvent mixture¹⁰. Generally, Walden rule holds better for larger and not heavily hydrated ions and hence having more or less the same effective radius in various solvents. Using the relation¹¹,

$$\Lambda_0\eta_0 = 1/6 \pi rT$$

where r is the effective radius of the concerned ion, it has

been possible to derive the values of r for the cation of the octahedral Co^{III} complex. As evident from Table 1, the value of r decreases with increase in methanol content upto $X_{\text{MeOH}} = 0.36$ and thereafter increases in methanol-rich region. The smaller $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ value in water-rich region may be due to the large effective radius of the cation, whereas the maximum value of $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ at $X_{\text{MeOH}} = 0.36$ corresponds to minimum value of r . A noticeable decrease in the solvation size of other solutes in water-rich mixtures has also been reported by others¹². The $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ in these solvents increases and then decreases after passing through a maxima¹³. It is thus apparent that its variation with the solvent compositions is due to an electrochemical equilibrium between the cations with the solvent molecules on one hand and the selective solvation of ions on the other with the change in the composition of the mixed solvents and temperature of the solution.

The values of $\Delta S_{\text{as}}^\circ$, $\Delta H_{\text{as}}^\circ$ and $\Delta G_{\text{as}}^\circ$ at different temperatures and in different solvents are shown in Table 2. The values of the K_A of the complexes decrease with rise in temperature until the $K_{A(\text{min})}$ is reached at t_{min} which is the characteristics of the anions. Beyond t_{min} , these values increase gradually. The presence of t_{min} was explained due to the weak hydration of the anion related to their structure-breaking properties³. The increase in the value of K_A beyond t_{min} is supported by increase of entropy changes. A positive entropy change has been explained on the assumption that the 'iceberg' structure around the cation is broken when association takes place leading to an increase in the degree of disorderliness¹⁴.

As expected, the free energy changes become more negative at higher percentage of methanol, which indicates that ion-pair association is favoured with lowering of dielectric constant of the medium. The lowering of K_A values with rise in temperature upto t_{min} is reflected by negative ΔH° values. Since the reaction is exothermic at higher temperatures, ion-association decreases. Above t_{min} , K_A values increase with increase in temperature, which is supported by positive ΔH° values as shown in Table 2. Above t_{min} ion-association is endothermic, so ion-association increases with increase in temperature.

Conclusion : K_A s have minimum values generally at 25°. $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ is maximum at $X_{\text{MeOH}} = 0.36$ in which η is maximum. At a particular temperature, as expected, r is inversely proportional to $\Lambda_0\eta_0$. Solvent-solvent interaction is maximum where η of solvent mixture is maximum. With the increase in X_{MeOH} , progressive disruption of water structure occurs and the ions become solvated with methanol. Further, thermodynamic parameters support the variation of K_A with temperature.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters ΔG° (kJ mol⁻¹), ΔH° (kJ mol⁻¹) and ΔS° (kJ mol⁻¹) of Co^{III} complex α -alanine bis-biguanide-Co^{III} iodide in water + methanol mixtures using Shedlovsky method

X_{methanol}	ΔG°	ΔH°	$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$	ΔG°	ΔH°	$10^3 \Delta S^\circ$
	(T = 278.15 K)			(T = 283.15 K)		
0.0000	-12.38	-42.31	-107.59	-12.29	-46.39	-120.46
0.0588	-12.60	-40.10	-098.87	-12.51	-43.60	-109.78
0.1233	-12.80	-32.01	-069.06	-12.69	-31.21	-065.41
0.1942	-13.03	-34.56	-077.43	-13.04	-39.34	-092.90
0.2727	-13.41	-36.79	-084.05	-13.38	-40.71	-096.50
0.3600	-13.47	-29.49	-057.60	-13.51	-33.24	-069.68
0.4576	-13.73	-32.89	-068.88	-13.80	-38.74	-088.08
0.5676	-13.96	-27.46	-048.54	-14.03	-31.37	-061.24
0.6923	-14.11	-21.13	-025.24	-14.25	-27.76	-037.14
0.8351	-14.36	-21.89	-027.07	-14.50	-25.67	-039.45
1.0000	-14.65	-20.89	-22.45	-14.76	-23.19	-029.78
	(T = 288.15 K)			(T = 293.15 K)		
0.0000	-11.84	-33.60	-075.52	-11.76	-36.53	-84.50
0.0588	-12.24	-39.13	-093.32	-12.10	-39.13	-92.21
0.1233	-12.50	-24.74	-042.48	-12.51	-26.72	-48.48
0.1942	-12.86	-37.57	-85.76	-12.74	-37.79	-85.46
0.2727	-13.12	-34.55	-74.38	-13.03	-33.85	-71.05
0.3600	-13.42	-32.59	-66.52	-13.35	-32.59	-63.06
0.4576	-13.84	-49.04	-123.63	-14.01	-39.92	-88.40
0.5676	-14.03	-33.98	-69.24	-14.01	-39.83	-88.09
0.6923	-14.26	-24.41	-35.25	-14.30	-27.23	-44.08
0.8351	-14.75	-26.27	-39.97	-14.56	-29.98	-52.60
1.0000	-14.79	-23.08	-28.77	-14.84	-23.25	-28.69
	(T = 303.15 K)			(T = 308.15 K)		
0.0000	-12.20	41.50	177.14	-12.90	51.77	209.84
0.0588	-12.51	40.13	173.64	-13.13	45.80	191.23
0.1233	-13.02	37.07	165.24	-13.51	36.23	161.42
0.1942	-13.30	52.86	218.32	-13.59	50.61	209.31
0.2727	-13.54	42.62	185.26	-14.08	41.34	179.84
0.3600	-13.87	39.90	177.37	-14.41	39.99	176.53
0.4576	-14.12	51.65	216.94	-14.70	48.48	205.05
0.5676	-14.46	37.71	172.09	-15.00	37.73	171.10
0.6923	-14.27	24.52	129.60	-15.19	23.58	125.73
0.8351	-15.05	28.65	144.12	-15.52	28.70	143.49
1.0000	-15.33	21.74	122.27	-15.85	27.68	141.28
	(T = 313.15 K)					
0.0000	-13.38	47.32	193.85			
0.0588	-13.67	45.51	189.00			
0.1233	-13.99	35.03	156.53			
0.1942	-14.46	49.23	203.39			
0.2727	-14.58	39.91	174.00			
0.3600	-14.96	40.46	176.96			
0.4576	-15.23	45.63	194.36			
0.5676	-15.50	36.95	167.51			
0.6923	-15.61	23.77	125.77			
0.8351	-15.97	28.08	140.67			
1.0000	-16.40	31.34	152.46			

Experimental

The octahedral Co^{III} complex, α -alanine bis-biguanidecobalt(III) iodide was prepared according to the reported procedure¹⁵. The purity of the sample was determined by conventional chemical analyses and spectral measurements. The values were in good agreement with the literature values. Methanol was treated by the standard procedure¹⁶. Water of specific conductance of the order $< 3 \times 10^{-6}$ S cm⁻¹ was used for preparing aqueous solutions of methanol with $X_{\text{MeOH}} = 0.0588, 0.1233, 0.1942, 0.2727, 0.3600, 0.4576, 0.5676, 0.6923, 0.8351$ and 1.0000 . All the solutions were prepared by dissolving weighed samples of the electrolyte in solvent mixtures (w/w). All the viscosity, dielectric constant, density and ion-conductance values were interpolated from literature values¹⁷. A Systronics 304 conductivity bridge (accuracy $\pm 0.1\%$) with a dip-type immersion conductivity cell was used. The conductance was measured in the temperature range 5–40°. The experiments were repeated 2-3 times with different concentrations of the solution ranging from 1.5×10^{-3} to 6.6×10^{-4} g equiv dm⁻³. Equivalent conductivities were corrected for the conductivity of the solvent concerned.

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References

- 1 R M Fuoss, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1958, **80**, 5059, R Fernandez-Prini, "Physical Chemistry of Organic Solvent Systems", eds A C Covington and T Dickinson, Plenum Press, London, 1973, R M Fuoss, *J Phys Chem*, 1978, **82**, 2427, A Mukhopadhyay, A Nandi, M Pal and S Bagchi, *Indian J Chem, Sect A*, 1994, **33**, 297
- 2 A Mukhopadhyay, M R Chattopadhyay and M Pal, *Indian J Chem, Sect A*, 1997, **36**, 94
- 3 H Yokoyama and T Ohta, *Bull Chem Soc Jpn*, 1988, **61** 3073, 1989, **62**, 345, H Yokoyama, *Bull Chem Soc Jpn*, 1984 **57**, 1307
- 4 T Shedlovsky and R L Kay, *J Phys Chem* 1956, **60** 151
- 5 B Per, *Acta Chem Scand, Ser A*, 1977 **31**, 869
- 6 N Papadopoulos and G Ritzoulis, *Chim Chronika (New Series)* 1986, **15**, 193 (*Chem Abstr*, **107**, 29031)
- 7 S Glasstone, "An Introduction to Electrochemistry", East-West Press, New Delhi, 1942
- 8 H Yokoyama and H Kon, *J Phys Chem*, 1991, **95**, 8959
- 9 U G K Raju, B Sethuram and T N Rao, *Bull Chem Soc Jpn*, 1982, **55**, 293
- 10 C G R Nair, R L Kumari and P Indrasenan, *Talanta*, 1978, **25**, 525
- 11 J I Bhat and P Bindu, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1995, **72**, 788
- 12 E Hawlicka and R Grabowski, *Naturforsch Z, Teil A*, 1991 **46**, 122, R K Swain, S C Das and B Behra, *J Electrochim Soc India*, 1990, **39**, 89
- 13 J F Coetzee and C D Ritchie, "Solute-Solvent Interactions", Marcel-Dekker, New York, 1976, Vol 2
- 14 M K De and R L Dutta, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1975, **52**, 67
- 15 B Anjana and R L Dutta, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1975, **52**, 1002
- 16 A Wiesberger, "Techniques in Organic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1955, Vol 7
- 17 C D Hodgman, R C Weast and S M Selby, "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", Chemical Rubber Publishing Co, Cleaveland, 1956-57, p 2257, Y Y Akhadov, "Dielectric Properties of Binary Solutions — A Data Handbook", Pergamon, Oxford, 1981 p 274, J Timmermanns, "The Physicochemical Constants of Binary Systems in Concentrated Solutions", Interscience, New York, Vol 4, p 786